

SELFHEALING COMPOSITES: INFLUENCE OF AGENT FRACTION

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ABSTRACT

Polymer composites used in structural applications are subjected to dynamic loads that can generate fatigue-induced microcracks. As these microcracks grow and merge, they lead to material failure, thereby reducing the service life of the component. To address this challenge, a promising strategy involves the development of smart self-healing polymers that, similar to biological systems, respond to damage by activating self-repair mechanisms, effectively enhancing the durability and lifespan of the material. This study investigates the interlaminar shear behavior of 5HS carbon fiber/epoxy composites containing varying amounts of the self-healing agent EMAA, processed via RTM. It examines the influence of agent content on mechanical performance and confirms, through thermal analysis, the feasibility of laminate fabrication, though particle dispersion may limit agent volume. ANOVA results show that EMAA content has a higher effect on mechanical response than internal dispersion. Weibull analysis indicates a linear decrease in shear strength with increased EMAA due to reduced stiffness from its ductile nature. Healing was most effective in interlaminar regions, achieving up to 62% recovery in shear strength, 106% in toughness, and 57% crack area reduction. Predictive modeling supports optimizing healing agent levels to meet design needs while reducing experimental effort and cost.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites with continuous fibers are extensively employed in aerospace applications. From 1980s, the AV-8B aircraft incorporated CFRP in 27% of its components, followed by the Boeing 787 that increased to 50% in its fuselage structure in 2000. More recently, advancements in urban air mobility (UAM) have been directed toward achieving fully fiber-reinforced structural designs, aiming for 100% composite reinforcement [1].

The use of RTM process for manufacturing high fiber volume fraction composite parts replacing autoclave manufacturing is quickly gaining momentum [2-3]. RTM manufactured components can also be co-cured with stiffener and rib structures. Although this reduces assembly time it opens up the possibility of poor mechanical properties in through the thickness direction [4] with damage usually occurring at the fiber/matrix interface in the form of microcracks or micro delamination [5], influencing adversely the fracture toughness [6].

Micro cracks can compromise the structural integrity of a vehicle and can reduce the vehicle life or result in a potentially injury of passenger safety. In recent years many repair techniques have been developed by transportation industry, and the goal of these repair methods is to fix visible damages on

composite polymer structure, however, for invisible damage inside the component during service life, traditional methods of repairing are not effective [7].

One emerging approach for mitigating or preventing damage is the use of healing agents, especially considering the high costs associated with replacing failed components. Incorporating self-healing agents offers the potential to enhance the safe operational lifespan of structural parts [8-10].

Since 2008, thermoplastic polymers have been explored as self-healing agents in high-performance composites, with the goal of addressing microcracks generated under mechanical stress [11]. These polymers act by interpenetrating into the damaged regions and forming chemical bonds at the crack surfaces, thereby helping to prevent failure. Meure et al. [12] incorporated EMAA (polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid) into an epoxy matrix, producing particles around 250 μm in size via cryogenic grinding and impact milling. Although this approach reduced the energy needed for activation, it also compromised the mechanical integrity of the healing material. The same researchers later examined the influence of pressure on healing, using EMAA films in epoxy systems. They identified gas bubble formation and chemical interactions involving oxirane, amine, and hydroxyl groups, and applied increased pressure to suppress the bubbles [13].

Further work by Varley et al. [14] revealed that ionomers in EMAA could effectively repair impact damage, triggered by ionic activation and reversible thermal behavior. Additives were shown to enhance plasticization and ion cluster mobility, which improved healing performance. Additionally, EMAA and EMA (polyethylene-co-methyl acrylate) have been utilized as co-polymeric healing agents in prepreg-based composites, where they were converted from pellets into thin films through hot pressing [15].

However, the presence of the self-healing agent in the polymeric resin introduces a new phase into the matrix, which can significantly alter the elastic behavior of the composite, which raises the following question: what is the influence of the healing agent fraction on the mechanical behavior of the material? Then, there is a requirement to know about the material's post-repair properties, analyzing the distribution of the agent within the material regions, and employing statistical tools to validate the results and predict the materials behavior, aiming to reduce both project time and cost.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The manufacturing process employed was the resin transfer molding (RTM) Radius 2100cc RTM Injector according to the Figure 1

Figure 1 – RTM system

The self-healing thermoplastic agent was cryogenically milled using a high-energy grinder, then sieved through a 100-mesh screen to obtain a fine particle as it can see in the Fig. 2, which were subsequently blended with the resin prior to molding. This mixture was injected into the fiber reinforcement within closed mold under regulated thermal and pressure conditions.

Figure 2 - Schematic steps of the thermoplastic self-healing process. (1) Pellets; (2) frozen pellets with liquid N₂; (3) impact mill; (4) sieve, and (5) self-healing powder (150–250 μm) [16]

Processing parameters settled for both laminates are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Processing parameters

Laminate	Injection pressure MPa	Vacuum level [MPa]	Injection temperature (°C)	Curing cycle (min)
<i>A and B</i>	0.2	0.05	125	180-240

The fiber preforms consisted of eight symmetrically arranged layers, achieving a fiber volume fraction of 55%. Composite samples were sectioned using a metallographic cutter from allied high-tech products, equipped with a diamond blade, following the dimensional specifications outlined in ASTM D2344. For microscopy evaluation, specimens were embedded in Bakelite and cure at 170°C for 7.5 min, polished with diamond suspensions (9 μm to 1 μm) and finished with 0.05 μm alumina suspension. Cross-sectional image was performed using a Tescan Vega 3 scanning electron microscope., according to the ref. [17].

3 RESULTS

The average and standard deviation measurement data of self-healing fraction in the laminates composite processed by RTM is shown in Table 2. The reference composite is called A without adding a healing agent (i.e., 0%). The C-B laminate represents a composite with 2.41% of self-healing agent, while the C-C represents a laminate with 9.79% of self-healing agent average fraction. Through the image treatment, it was possible to measure the diameter size distribution of self-healing particles along the C-B and C-C composites, as shown in the histogram of Fig. 3a. Both composite families had the same processing procedures, modifying only the EMAA particle fraction. For specimen C-B, the largest diameter concentration is found in the range 20–30 μm (i.e., 41.73%), with a low fraction for particles >100 μm (3.98%).

Table 2: Agent fraction data.

Healing agent Fraction		
laminate	Average	Standard deviation
<i>A</i>	2.41	1.60
<i>B</i>	9.79	2.30

The self-healing particle diameter distribution in A and B coposites was measured and it was seen that in A, most particles fall within the 20–30 μm range (41.73%), with few exceeding 100 μm (3.98%). In contrast, increasing the thermoplastic content in B shifts the peak to 60–70 μm (31.08%) and raises the >100 μm fraction to 17.29%. This suggests higher particle agglomeration in B, increasing size variation and standard deviation. Higher healing agent content led to particle coalescence during manufacturing, enlarging particles and reducing dispersion uniformity. This inhomogeneity can affect self-healing efficiency, as a more uniform particle distribution improves the likelihood of crack interaction and closure through thermoplastic flow and reconnection [18].

Irregular shapes were no significant—0.05% in A and 0.09% in B laminates. As with diameter distribution, B showed higher morphological variation due to particle coalescence. Despite this, circular and elliptical shapes remained consistent across both laminates, indicating that coalescence increased particle size in B without altering morphology. While larger particles may improve localized healing, they reduce macro-healing effectiveness by concentrating the agent in fewer regions, limiting its interaction with diverse cracks [19].

The fig. 3 presents the ILSS curves for the reference laminates (no self-healing agent), the laminate with 2.41% healing agent before (A) and after repair (AB), and with 9.79% agent before (B) and after repair (RB).

Figure 3 - ILSS curves [1].

The stress–displacement curve (Fig. 3) shows a reduced stiffness attributed to the addition and increasing EMAA content compared the reference. After testing, self-healing samples were heated at 150 °C for 30 min. activate healing. The post-healing curves exhibit smoother behavior and lower load capacity, reflecting the ductile nature of the thermoplastic agent compared to the highly crosslinked epoxy matrix [20].

ANOVA was performed to assess the contribution of the self-healing agent fraction to the variability in mechanical properties and to test the null hypothesis (H_0) of no significant difference between fractions. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) assumes the agent fraction affects mechanical performance. Analysis was conducted in Minitab 18 with $\alpha = 0.05$ and 95% confidence, comparing between-group variance (agent fraction) to within-group variance (test repeatability).

The equations used in the ANOVA method to calculate the F-factor are shown in Table 3, where n is the number of data points, C is the group number, x_i is the group mean, \bar{x} is the overall mean, x_{ji} is each individual value, and the F-factor indicates whether the self-repair fraction's variation has higher variance than the mechanical response's standard deviation. The p-value is tabulated based on the degrees of freedom and F-value.

Table 3 - Structured form of the ANOVA model

Variation	SS-total	DF	MS	F-factor
Between-groups	$S_a = \sum_{i=1}^c n(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^2$	$V_a = C - 1$	$SM_a = \frac{S_a}{V_a}$	$F = \frac{SM_a}{V_b}$
Whithin-groups	$S_b = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^n (\bar{x}_{ji} - \bar{x})^2$	$V_b = n - 1$	$SM_b = \frac{S_b}{V_b}$	

n = number of experimental observations; C = group identifier (or group index); \bar{x}_i , mean of the i -th group; \bar{x} = grand mean (overall mean across all groups); \bar{x}_{ji} = individual observation j within group i ; F = F -statistic, representing the ratio of the between-group mean square to the within-group mean square

The variation in interlaminar shear strength was characterized using a two-parameter Weibull distribution, as presented in Equation (1) [20]. This distribution enables the estimation of failure probability across different reliability levels and is widely adopted for analyzing the variability in brittle failure of composite materials. Linearization of the Weibull distribution was performed using Equation (2), allowing for the estimation of the shape parameter (m) and the scale parameter (X_U).

$$P(\bar{x}) = \bar{e} \left[-\frac{x_c}{X_u} \right]^m \quad (1)$$

$$\ln \left[\left(\frac{1}{1 - P(\bar{x})} \right) \right] = m \cdot \ln(x_c) - m \cdot \ln(x_u) \quad (2)$$

In addition to the probabilistic approach, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was applied to model and predict the mechanical behavior as a function of key processing parameters, specifically the self-healing agent fraction (SH , in %) and displacement (D , in mm). This approach enabled the development of predictive models for both the pre-healing condition (σ_N) and the post-healing condition (σ_R), as described in Equation (3).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i \bar{x}_i + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j \bar{x}_j + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} \bar{x}_i^2 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{jj} \bar{x}_j^2 + \sum_{j=i}^k \beta_{ji} \bar{x}_i \bar{x}_j \quad (3)$$

Where Y represents the predicted response, and the variables x_i and x_j correspond to the levels of the processing parameters, the beta coefficients (β) represent the constant term, the linear effects, and the interaction effects between the variables.

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to assess the influence of the self-healing agent fraction on the mechanical properties. Prior to the healing process (Table 4), the between-group variance was found to be statistically significant ($F > F_{critical}$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that variations in the self-healing agent fraction have a substantial effect on the mechanical response. The contribution percentage (PC) of the between-group variance reached **87.6%**, whereas the within-group variance accounted for only **12.4%**, confirming the dominant influence of the healing agent fraction on the composite's performance.

Table 4. ANOVA pre-repair action

Variance	SS	DF	MS	F-ratio	p-values	Fcritico	%
within-group	65.213	5	13.04	0.72	0.620	3.32	12.40
between-group	460.67	2	230.34	12.79	0.001	4.10	87.60
Total	525.89	10					-

Sum of Squares (SS); Degrees of Freedom (DF); Mean Square (MS); Variation between sample means / Variation within samples (F – F-ratio) and Percentage Contribution (%)

Following the healing process (Table 5), an inverse trend was observed. The within-group variance increased substantially (% = 76.56%), while the between-group contribution decreased (% = 23.43%). Moreover, both F-values were lower than Fcritical, with p-values exceeding 0.05, indicating that the effect of the self-healing agent fraction became statistically insignificant post-repair. This behavior is attributed to the inherent variability in crack propagation and closure, as well as the stochastic nature of damage localization after failure, which introduced higher dispersion in the post-healing mechanical results.

Table 5. ANOVA post-repair action.

Variance	SS	DF	MS	F-factor	p-value	Fcritical	%
Within-group	45.56	5	9.11	0.45	0.79	5.05	76.56
Between-group	13.94	1	13.94	0.69	0.44	6.60	23.43
Total	59.50	6					

Sum of Squares (SS); Degrees of Freedom (DF); Mean Square (MS); Variation between sample means / Variation within samples (F – F-ratio) and Percentage Contribution (%)

Weibull distribution modeling (Figure 4) demonstrated an excellent fit to the experimental data, both before and after the healing process, with a coefficient of determination $R^2 > 0.99$.

Fig. 4 - Sensitivity analysis of the predicted ultimate shear stress pre- and post-healing.

The analysis revealed that increasing the self-healing agent fraction led to a progressive reduction in maximum interlaminar shear strength at a given reliability level. This reduction is associated with particle agglomeration effects and lower fracture consolidation efficiency at higher healing agent concentrations.

A three-dimensional Response Surface Methodology (RSM) surface was also generated, effectively describing the mechanical response as a function of SH and D, enabling predictive capabilities beyond experimentally tested conditions. The models presented a maximum error of less than **3.9%**, with **R² > 0.93**, demonstrating robust predictive accuracy. The resulting predictive equations are as follows 3 and 4:

- **Pre-healing mechanical behavior:**

$$\sigma_N = -7.33 - 1.11SH + 195.46D + 0.067SH^2 - 179.25D^2 \cdot D \quad (3)$$

- **Post-healing mechanical behavior:**

$$\sigma_R = -3.11 - 0.28SH + 126.23D - 0.037SH^2 - 99.90D^2 - 0.63SH \cdot D \quad (4)$$

These predictive models provide a valuable tool for design optimization of self-healing laminated composites, supporting the selection of the optimal healing agent fraction to balance mechanical performance and repair efficiency. Additionally, the generated response surfaces contribute to reducing experimental efforts, time, and costs associated with mechanical testing.

The findings highlight that although the inclusion of self-healing agents enhances damage tolerance, excessive fractions lead to a notable reduction in mechanical properties without proportional gains in repair efficiency. Therefore, optimizing the healing agent content is essential for maintaining a balance between structural integrity and autonomous repair functionality.

4 CONCLUSIONS

It was evaluated the influence of thermoplastic self-healing agent fraction on the shear behavior of CFRP through comprehensive mechanical and statistical analyses. The distribution of self-healing particles, morphology, and repair performance were characterized. Key findings include:

- Stiffness values is reduced with the addition of the self-healing agent due to reduced bond density in the thermoplastic within the thermoset matrix;
- Higher agent fractions lowered repair efficiency, attributed to intralaminar fracture and thermoplastic coalescence (larger particle size), indicating a threshold for injection processing;
- ANOVA revealed that the agent fraction had a higher influence than internal variation among similar laminates prior to repair;
- Self-healing achieved average recoveries of 62% in shear strength, 106% in toughness modulus, and a 57% reduction in crack size;
- Predictive modeling of interlaminar shear behavior identified optimal agent fractions that meet design goals while reducing time and cost.

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